

Aesthetic Rehabilitation of Maxillary Anterior Incisor; One-Step fiber post cementation and core build-up in Endodontically treated tooth—A Case Report.

Anupam Gupta¹, Arun Verma², Swapn Rai³

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¹PG Student,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki.

²Professor and Head,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki.

³Professor,
Department of Conservative
Dentistry and Endodontics,
Chandra Dental College and
Hospital, Barabanki.

Abstract

The incidence of maxillary anterior teeth being injured is very high as they are anteriorly placed in the arch, and they have a protrusive eruptive pattern. Maxillary anterior tooth injury can cause changes in a patient's appearance as well as function and thus leading to a psychological impact.

The application of intracanal post in root canal treated tooth improves the retention of eventual restoration. The fiber post has a modulus of elasticity very similar to dentin, and they strengthen the remaining tooth structure and increase tooth fracture resistance. The aim of this case report is to emphasize the successful clinical outcome following rehabilitation of an endodontically treated tooth with severe coronal destruction and weakened root structure. This clinical case report addresses the step-by-step of the application of a core-and-post system that uses a single resin composite material to fiber post cementation and core build-up in a maxillary central incisor.

Keywords: Post; Core; Fiber post; restorative dentistry; Endodontically treated tooth; Fracture strength; Esthetic Rehabilitation; Anterior tooth;

Introduction

Endodontically treated teeth that show coronal structure destruction and have undergone extensive restorations are usually rebuilt with post and core followed by prosthetic crown restoration.¹⁻² Cast post and core has been traditionally used due to its high mechanical strength and desirable fit in the root canal.³⁻ However, teeth restored by such systems may show more frequent oblique/horizontal fractures in the middle third of the root,^{9,10} or vertical root fractures caused by both increased stress concentration in the apical region of the post and a difference in the Young's modulus between dentin and metal.¹ An ideal core and post improves the bio mechanical stability of an abutment tooth preventing debonding and root fracture or fracture of the abutment.¹¹ Therefore, over the last decades, prefabricated glass fiber posts have been used as an alternative for custom metallic posts.^{12,13}

Due to improvements in adhesive techniques, resin composite scores and glass fiber posts have become increasingly prevalent. The Young's modulus of resin composites, in contrast to that of the cast post and core, is more comparable to that of the dentin, which results in decreased stress concentration under occlusal forces and prevents catastrophic root fractures.^{7,14} Moreover, the adhesive cement layer at the post/dentin interface can absorb the occlusal forces, which decreases the occurrence of root fractures.¹⁵ According to some authors,

the incidence of fiber posts fractures are lower and the survival and success rates are higher in comparison to teeth restored with no post¹⁶ or with cast post and core.¹⁷

This case report addresses the clinical use of dual cure resin along with a post system (Paracore, Coltene Inc, USA) that employs a single material for both cementation of the fiber post and core build-up in tooth.^{18,19} Furthermore, such materials show similar or lower polymerization shrinkage in comparison to conventional and/or flowable composite resins, and similar fracture strength to nano hybrid composite resins,²⁰ and can be used in restorations of endodontically treated teeth with extensive structure loss.^{21,22} Despite the development of novel materials and techniques over the past years, major challenges and controversy regarding restoration of endodontically treated teeth still remain, mainly when the root is weakened and the ferrule is either limited, or absent.

A clinical case series of two cases presented clarifies the technical steps of post and core procedure and discusses the benefits of the single adhesive material in relation to the widely used conventional procedures²².

Case Report

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Case 1: An 18-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Chandra Dental College and Hospital, Barabanki, with the chief complaint of fractured upper left front teeth with a unesthetic appearance of face, after sustaining trauma due to accidental fall. On intraoral examination, there was no pain and swelling. On vitality testing using cold test and electric pulp tester, the tooth tested non-vital. Radio lucency involving enamel, dentin and pulp was seen in radiographic examination. On the basis of clinical and radiographic findings we made the diagnosis of Ellis class III fracture with non vital tooth. Patient has been counselled about treatment procedures to be performed i.e. Root canal treatment followed by post and core in order to rehabilitate lost tooth structure and Consent has been signed from the patient before initiation of the treatment.

Fig 1: Pre operative Clinical Picture

After administration of local anaesthesia, Due to absence of adequate coronal tooth structure access cavity was prepared without rubber dam and isolation was achieved using cotton roll. Canal orifice was located. Working length was determined and canal was prepared up to 25/0.06 using NiTi rotary file system. The canal was obturated with Gutta percha point and AH Plus sealer.

Crown lengthening procedure was performed recontouring gum tissue to obtain a minimum ferule length of 2mm. After this, tooth and post space preparation was done under rubber dam isolation in the central canal using peeso reamers size 1 and 2 leaving 3-4mm apical gutta percha intact. Fiber post selection was done of appropriate size and placement is done at the length of post space preparation to check proper fitting of fiber post. Prefabricated fiber post was cemented using dual cure resin cement in the post space and the core build up was subsequently done using Paracore (Coltene inc, USA). Finishing of the core was done around the buccal and palatal surface as well as proximal margins using polishing burs / Disc.

Case 2: A 24-year-old female patient was attended in the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Chandra Dental College and Hospital, Barabanki,

Fig 2: Pre-op. RVG Fig 3: WL Determination Fig 4: Master Conefit Fig 5: Obturation

Fig 6: Post space Fig 7: Post Space Fig 8: Post Placement Fig 9: Curing of resin cement Preparation RVG

Fig 10: Core build up Fig 11: completion of Core build up

complaining of pain in the upper right front tooth region. The patient gave a history of sharp, shooting, and continuous pain that was aggravated on the intake of hot and cold beverages. On clinical examination there was loss of significant tooth structure due to long-standing decay and chipping of the tooth structure. Radio lucency involving pulp was seen in radiographic examination. On the basis of clinical and radiographic findings diagnosis for this case is Ellis class III fracture with vital tooth. Patient has been counselled about treatment procedures to be performed i.e. Root canal treatment followed by post and core in order to rehabilitate lost tooth structure and Consent has been signed from patient before initiation of the treatment.

After administration of local anaesthesia, under rubber dam isolation access cavity was prepared and canal orifice located. Working length was determined and canal was

Fig 12: Pre Operative Radiograph (OPG) Fig 13: Pre op Clinical View

prepared up to 25/0.06 by NiTi Rotary file system. Sectional obturation was done with Gutta Percha point and AH Plus sealer. After this, tooth preparation was done followed by post space preparation in the central canal using peeso reamers size 1 and 2 leaving 3-4mm apical gutta percha intact. Fiber post selection was done of appropriate size and placement is done at the length of post space preparation to check proper fitting of fiber post.

After adhesion procedures, the fiber post was cemented into the root canal and the core was made using the single Paracore (coltene), which is a dual-cure highly filled (70 wt%) resin composite delivered in a dual-barreled syringe, which

favors direct and accurate intra oral applications.

The tooth was subjected to finishing around the buccal and palatal surface as well as proximal margins.

Discussion

A pleasing smile with healthy teeth is an integral part of overall appearance and self-esteem. Anterior crown fractures lead to discomfort and serious psychological, esthetic, functional and phonetic problems that can affect social

Fig 14: Rubber Dam Isolation Fig 15: WL determination Fig 16: Conefit Fig 17: Sectional Obturation & post space preparation

Fig 18: Post placement Fig 19: Etching of Canal Fig 20: Curing of resin cement Fig 21: Post operative

Fig 23: Core build up

relationships.²

In the restoration of anterior teeth, many factors are to be considered depending on the patient's expectations. Restoring such teeth using materials with a similar elastic modulus to dentin appears advantageous due to the reduced risk of root fractures.¹

The current trend in dentistry is to preserve tooth structure to a greater degree with minimum invasion. Thus, tendency has changed starting from the use of cast posts to prefabricated posts that allow a minimum dental preparation with quick resolution.²¹

Root canal-treated teeth are structurally and mechanically different than vital teeth. Endodontically treated teeth have reduced fracture resistance. When there is extensive loss of hard tissue, additional reinforcement of root canal treated tooth is achieved using intracanal posts.^{23,24} Restoring such teeth with materials having similar elastic modulus to dentin is preferred as they are less prone to fracture.²⁴

Complicated crown fracture has been traditionally restored with a cast post. Evolution in adhesive dentistry has resulted in the use of resin-based fiber posts for reinforcing the restoration of endodontically treated teeth.²⁵

Fiber post has a modulus of elasticity similar to dentin and increases endodontically treated teeth's resistance to fracture.²⁶ Previously fiber posts were radiolucent but recent

fiber posts are radiopaque. They even conduct light for the polymerization of resin-based luting cement. Because of these advantages, fiber post is preferred for restorations with composite resins.²⁷⁻³⁰

Bonding of fiber posts to root canal dentin improves the distribution of forces applied along the root, thus decreasing the risk of root fracture and thereby contributing to the reinforcement of the remaining tooth structure.^{31,32,33} Studies by Gbadebo, Ajayi et. al. concluded that fiber post presented a significantly higher survival rate than did metal post.^{34,35}

The fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth is dependent mainly on the amount of remaining tooth structure, the quality of adhesion and the type of post as posts increase the fracture resistance of the root. Oliveira and colleagues concluded that the greatest factor influencing the strength of endodontically treated teeth was the amount of remaining tooth structure. Because of these properties, fiber post was used in the above mentioned cases to restore and strengthen the fractured teeth.²⁶

Freedman stated that the main function of the post is to anchor the post-and-core complex within the radicular portion of the remaining tooth. A post that can be bonded to tooth structure improves its ability to retain the entire foundation. The use of post enables to reinforce the strength of the lost tooth structure. Posts placed in the canal subsequent to endodontic treatment increases the strength of the tooth and helps it to withstand the masticatory forces directed along the tooth.^{21,22}

Conclusion

Restoration of teeth after endodontic treatment is an important part of the restorative practice in dentistry. Preservation of coronal dental tissue, the use of posts with properties similar to dentin and effective post adhesion are the most important factors for the successful clinical performance of restored endodontically treated teeth.

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